

METHODOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF WORKING ON LITERARY CONCEPTS IN THE CLASSES OF MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY OF PRIMARY GRADE

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Annotation: In this article, within the framework of reading literacy, the formation of correct, fast, conscious, expressive reading skills in the student, raising them from an ordinary book reader to the level of a thoughtful, creative reader; to expand knowledge about the environment and existence through reading, to enrich their worldview; formation of elementary literary concepts in thinking; reading and understanding any style of text; it is intended to improve critical and creative thinking skills.

Key words: education, upbringing, literary concept, image, critical thinking, artistic work, perception, pedagogical technology, analysis.

Today, the new content of education and upbringing: raising the awareness of students; further improvement of the educational process; to raise teaching methods to the level of today's requirements; development of children's cognitive abilities at a high level; to achieve conscious and thorough assimilation of given knowledge and skills; aims to develop students' independent mental work skills.

In the National Curriculum (NCC), the main focus of teaching Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy is on the formation of four language skills: reading comprehension, listening comprehension, speaking and writing, and grammatical literacy. Forming correct, fast, conscious, expressive reading skills in the student within the framework of reading literacy, raising them from an ordinary book reader to the level of a thoughtful, creative reader; to expand knowledge about the environment and existence through reading, to enrich their worldview; formation of elementary literary concepts in thinking; reading and understanding any style of text; it is intended to improve critical and creative thinking skills.

In native language and reading literacy classes, students get acquainted with works about nature and society, the lives of people living in it, their past, and their current way of life. Pupils are given knowledge about nature, weather, natural resources, flora and fauna, etc. Attitudes are created in the process of learning. By imparting knowledge, the student's personality develops. Educational tasks are closely solved in classroom reading lessons.

Positive qualities of students are formed. They mature mentally and aesthetically. They acquire the basics of learning independently. All this is achieved in the process of reading

works of different genres and volumes, with different topics and contents, given in the textbooks of the primary class "Mother language and reading literacy". Therefore, it is appropriate to properly organize the process of reading and learning these works.

Elementary students especially love to read art samples. Studying a sample of artistic work helps to understand life through images, leaves a deep impression on children's hearts. An artistic work serves as an important tool in raising children to be spiritually mature people. It is also of great importance in their moral and aesthetic education.

Reading literary works of various genres, such as poems, stories, parables, fairy tales, riddles, inculcates the love of literature and mother tongue in students.

"It is not enough to understand a work of art, it is also necessary to feel it," said K. D. Ushinsky. Every reader who wants to understand the character traits of the characters in the literary work and the spirit of this work should get acquainted with its full content. It is also important to be able to analyze a work of art in order to understand it.

According to the goals and objectives of the reading and speech development program in primary education, students are taught to read correctly, consciously, fluently, quickly and expressively. In this process, children acquire the skills of working with books and develop a love for books.

It is necessary to take into account their age and level of knowledge in order to correctly form their imagination and understanding of the surrounding things and events in the minds of students. In this case, primary school students' ability to independently understand the content of the read text is further strengthened.

Various works and topics are included from the primary grade "Mother tongue and reading literacy" textbooks. The materials in them are intended to improve children's knowledge and skills in all aspects, to expand their levels by expanding their understanding of the surrounding life, interpersonal relationships, spiritual images of the people of our republic, their Motherland and existence. That is why the content of textbooks is to give children ideological, political, moral and aesthetic education; improving the skills of correct, fast, conscious and expressive reading; It is aimed at the implementation of important educational goals and tasks, such as further strengthening and generalization of some of the subjects learned by students in the primary classes, as well as preparing the ground for their successful studies in the next senior classes.

It is necessary to take into account their age and level of knowledge in order to correctly form their imagination and understanding of the surrounding things and events in the minds of students.

Elementary school students should have the following skills when working on the text:

- ❖ *to observe the consistent development of the story in the example of the read work;*
- ❖ *to be able to determine the logical cohesiveness of text parts;*
- ❖ *making a plan according to the content of the read text;*
- ❖ *choosing material to talk about the participants in the text read from the book;*
- ❖ *to evaluate the behavior of the characters of the text;*
- ❖ *creating a story about the characters of the read text;*
- ❖ *being able to retell the content of the text based on an independently prepared plan;*
- ❖ *being able to distinguish the main idea from the text independently;*

❖ *to be able to distinguish the difference in the meaning of the words found in the text;*

❖ *to choose figurative words and phrases from the text necessary to characterize nature and people;*

❖ *to be able to summarize the concepts of read fairy tales, parables, stories, poems.*

In the methodology of the analysis of an artistic work in elementary grades, the psychological characteristics of the perception of an artistic work of young students are taken into account. According to the investigations of psychologists, along with the components that serve to perceive and gain knowledge of the work, it also includes emotional-aesthetic feeling. Understanding an artistic work is not enough to understand it well. Perception of a work is a complex process, which involves the emergence of some kind of relationship to the work and the reality depicted in it. As a result of psychological tests, the psychological characteristics of young students' perception and evaluation of literary characters were studied, and it was determined that they have two different attitudes towards literary characters:

1. *Emotional attitude to the literary hero;*

2. *Elementary analysis.*

Students use their own personal and moral understanding to evaluate the characters in the play. Of course, such moral concepts are limited in young students. They often use the concepts of bravery, correctness, hard work, and goodness as moral qualities. They lack the vocabulary to describe the other qualities of the characters. The task of the teacher is to analyze with the students and introduce words describing the moral, intellectual and emotional qualities of the characters into their speech. This is one of the conditions for a good portrayal of the character of literary heroes.

It is necessary to take into account the psychological characteristics of students in order to ensure the conscious mastering of the work being read in reading classes.

In the current period, the tasks set before the school, the increase in the general development of students of junior school age, the achievements in the field of psychology and private methodology require changes in the content of reading and teaching methods in the classroom. In connection with this, the methodology of the analysis of the artistic work was improved: the repetition exercises were reduced, the exercises to develop the ability to express one's thoughts creatively and on the basis of the read text were increased, the work was done not on the parts of the work, but on the whole work, the independence of the students in explaining the idea and images of the work increased, various types of tasks were used in working on the text, technical tools and methods of advanced pedagogical technology were used more in education, etc.

In elementary grades, the work of art is analyzed based on the following important methodical rules:

1. Analyzing the content of the work and forming correct, fast, conscious, expressive reading skills are part of the same process (the task of explaining the content of the work is also a task of improving reading skills).

2. Explaining the ideological basis and theme of the work, its images, subject line, composition and pictorial means will serve well for the general development of students as individuals, as well as ensure the growth of connected speech (enrichment and activation of vocabulary).

3. Relying on students' life experience is the basis of conscious perception of the content of the work and a necessary condition for its analysis.

4. Studying in the classroom is considered as an effective means of activating students' cognitive activity, expanding their knowledge about the environment, and forming the foundations of a scientific outlook.

One of the important factors to consider when analyzing a work is its emotional impact on readers. Let the readers not only understand the main idea of the author, but also be excited by the story that the author is excited about. It is necessary to analyze the text to make the reader think, to determine whether his life experience corresponds to the evidence recorded by the author. During the analysis, the aesthetic value and artistic beauty of the work are also noted.

The reading methodology is based on the theoretical rules developed by literary studies, psychology, and pedagogy. In order to properly organize reading in the classroom, the teacher should take into account the specific features of the artistic work, the psychological basis of the reading process at different stages of education, and the features of understanding and mastering the text of students of junior school age.

In reading classes, the ability of students to distinguish between artistic work, to determine what kind of images the writer has used to reflect life events and create images, to read independently and to analyze the work is growing from class to class. Pupils begin to understand the content, idea and importance of the work of art by learning literary information.

As a result of studying literary concepts, students will learn that fiction is a type of art and that it is related to life. Along with the formation of literary concepts, the development of students' speech is also important.

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